

Vol:1, Issue: 4 pp: 557-563

JEL Code: Z13

HOQUE M., SHAMEEM A S M. (2020). "Teaching and Learning the Grammar of the English Language Plays a Crucial Role in the Context of EFL/ESL",

Vol: 1 Issue: 4 pp: 557-563

Keywords: *EFL/ESL context; communicative language teaching; grammar; grammar teaching.*

Article Type Review Article

**Teaching and Learning the Grammar of the English Language Plays
a Crucial Role in the Context of EFL/ESL**

Arrived Date
10.10.2020

Accepted Date
13.10.2020

Published Date
31.10.2020

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ABSTRACT

The grammatical competence of the English language plays a crucial role in the progress of language mastering. However, it is noted that the position of grammar is still underestimated in various EFL/ESL contexts, and grammar-oriented exams are explicit in practice rather than communicative instruction. As a consequence, many EFL/ESL learners are shown to be successful at grammar but yet cannot articulate fluently and precisely. The purpose of this paper is therefore to address grammar teaching, including the concepts and priorities of grammar teaching. It also discusses the positions and responsibilities of grammar in communicative language teaching (CLT) in the context of EFL/ESL. This paper also proposes several pedagogical consequences for teaching grammar in the sense of the EFL/ESL. This paper is hoped to contribute its part to highlight the role of grammar in the CLT and to shed more light on the inclusion of grammar teaching in the sense of the EFL/ESL.

INTRODUCTION

Academic success is measured not only by learning elements but also by successful aspects. Harun (Rashid, Hui, Shameem, Hoque, Islam, Nishi, Zamir, 2020). Fear is a negative emotion that can help you learn to be effective. In recent years, the English language has been considered as one of the most popular languages, and it has been used to serve learning and teaching at schools in Bangladesh (Rashid, Victor, Islam, Li, 2020). A global language is a language that has got a large number of speakers all over the world. English is considered as a tool of communication. Grammar is usually taught by using traditional methods before the availability of the computer in the classroom. Moreover, as it certifies that grammar lessons seem complex to students, students need to learn English grammar first when they learn the English language and teaching grammar is challenging. Most teachers always rely on blackboard and posters as their teaching aids. Due to the influences of teaching English from the beginning learners are familiar to do grammar exercises. Therefore, English grammar always plays a crucial role in learning the language.

People are not able to comprehend deeply without knowledge of grammar. Sentences without appropriate grammar structures are also hard for readers and listeners to fully understand the meaning. Even if the words or sentences do not put on correct grammar structures, it may cause misunderstanding when conveying information to listeners. It is the reason for learning English grammar and it cannot avoid learning English grammar. Besides English plays as a useful tool of communication in many fields about cultural, social, business working, and so on. It brings people to come closer and to achieve what they want in communication. It is highlighted that teachers are

The summary of this article was presented as a paper at the 1st International Conference of Social Science, Innovation and Educational Technologies (ICSSIET 2020) held online on 30 September 2020.
The completed version was not published before.

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known as a center of power instead of giving students chances to communicate in English (e.g., Denham, 1992; Tran & Seepho, 2016). However, Pradeep (2013, p. 482) states that “grammar is a very important part that cannot be neglected in teaching and studying English. Students can speak English more correctly if they are proficient in grammar”.

To use English grammar structures or forms applying in real contexts and paying interested in learning grammar communication, it is essential to look back on teaching English Grammar communicatively. This article mainly focuses on the three mainpoints of (1) discussing the grammar teaching including principles and goals of grammar teaching, (2) the positions and roles of English grammar in communicative language teaching (CLT) in the EFL/ESL context, and (3) some pedagogical implications on how to teach grammar communicatively in the EFL/ESL context.

Beliefs for teaching of grammar

It is better to bring real contexts in teaching English grammar. The real contexts will help teachers and learners attain desirable results. So how to bring practical contexts in English grammar lessons, it should have three main characteristics that a good context should attain: they are authentic, informative, and interesting. Firstly, the contexts should be authentic. When matters are close to life, it will bring many more effects on teaching and learning. And the most important thing is that it needs to provide full contents of the structures, usages, meanings, and some model samples that the learners can redo, regain and recover it well with what are happening in their real situation. (Lewis and Hill 1992; 28) state that the appropriateness of context can be achieved if the teacher brings something real and useful from the outside classroom.

Secondly, an informative context should be comprehensible and easy to remember. It also should have many clues to attain the target languages and provide various forms. The information on the different situation should be clear, useful, and practical with daily activities. Thirdly, learners always feel interested in real contexts. Learners also feel excited about learning, willing to study; play the roles, and eager for attending the class. They are ready to participate in any activities without hesitation. As (Ehrenworth & Vinton, 2005; 89) state that it should be made “seductive” in the way that the students cannot resist it but they have to “dig” it and “get their hand dirty”. It is also better for students to do by themselves, so they can remember knowledge longer and speak naturally. (Ur, 1996; 57) shows that the context should provide the background for a lot of languages using so that students can use the information not only for the repetition of model sentences but also for making their sentences. It is necessary to bring the contexts in teaching grammar communication that will help to attain effective results.

The concepts for creating tasks in the context

To attain the target language, the teachers need to help the learners know how to apply forms or structures in doing tasks, spoken languages, or written texts. Especially, learners can know how to recognize the form and meaning in the real situation, and they can produce both written and spoken form. It is vital to provide correct and meaningful sentences in appropriate contexts. Therefore, teachers need to design real contexts by using suitable model structures. While designing tasks, teachers should ask their learners some targets at least about presentation, practice, and consolidation. The most important thing is that the tasks should be related to the structures or form focused. Based on the structures, teachers may open widely diversified activities. Some activities enhance the learners to learn without any fear in the classroom such as Role Play, Games, Pair work, Interviews.

As (Ur, 1988; 6) states that when grammatical structures are taught, teachers are, or should be asking students to learn “a large number of different though related bits of knowledge and skills” which are recognition, identification, and production of the target language structure. (Hedge, 2000) considers that the presentation of grammar to learners should facilitate learning in many ways. It can provide input for noticing output and accurate forms of English; it can present high-frequency grammatical items explicitly to speed up learning; it can provide information about the communicative use of language structures by contextualizing them in spoken and written form. Furthermore, tasks should be

practical. It must be used very often in life. (Thornbury, 2001; 23) summarizes some rules of context, teaching grammar in context, the rules of using grammar structures, the ability to use and apply in real contexts, the rule of the economy, and the rule of appropriateness about the levels, needs, interests, expectations and learning styles of the students. The tasks should be various and they can satisfy the learners' needs as well as social needs. It should be combined different techniques to create a comfortable atmosphere which will help learners pay more interest in learning and have much more cooperation among others during the time implementing the tasks.

The Objectives of Grammar Teaching

The paper mentions three main goals in teaching grammar. Firstly, every student, from every background, should complete school with the ability to communicate comfortably and effectively in both spoken and written Standard English. They will be aware of when using Standard English is appropriate. It will be recognized that each learner will attain the languages in their ways, by doing various exercises, listening to the tapes recorded, or practicing speaking by themselves or with others even if they can acquire the targets in any environment. The most important thing is teachers should share effective skills of speaking, listening, reading, and writing. Besides, students should have various knowledge of grammar to talk freely and naturally in different situations.

Secondly, after finishing English courses learners must acquire basic knowledge as well as advanced knowledge about English grammar. They can use the grammatical structure, to analyze the grammatical structure of sentences in English texts, daily life conversation, and the ability to practice well simple sentences to complex paragraphs. Finally, with the purposes of proficiency in communication, learners should attain at least their goals for studying. When they can understand and master languages, they are easy to take part in society and deal with foreigners.

Therefore, grammar teaching sets the teaching of communicative competence as its goal. The ability to recognize and deeply will help to produce correct sentences and meaningful conversations. They can take the contents or keep giving much more other information.

The contributions of Grammar in Communicative Language Teaching (CLT)

Communicative Language Teaching does not include any English grammar. It only focuses on communication. (Spada, 2007; 275) points out that "Communicative Language Teaching means an exclusive focus on meaning". To discuss the contributions of grammar used in communication, there are some matters such as grammar helps to get the true meaning of talking. As can see that the foreigners also often get some mistakes when speaking, so to be good at grammar will help to hear and get the meaning of conversation easily and effectively. By contrast, without English grammar, you will not be able to understand the purpose of the speaker. Take these two sentences as an example: "I am in love with her and I was in love with her". It can be seen that the difference is very small (am - was), one is in the present meaning and one is in the past but the relationship between the speaker and "her" is very different in two cases. So it will cause some misunderstandings in communication. One more things are that to be good at grammar will help to perform appropriately and effectively to listeners. When having to talk, people may misunderstand the meaning if English grammar is used incorrectly. For example, with the phrase "He is a handsome boy", it can misinterpret that "He handsome boy", people still can understand. However, it is said that "He handsome boy", it will make the listener "confused". For complicated sentences, people who are straining their ears but can't understand what we say. Even if we are good at basic grammar it will be better. A good grammar foundation will help us convey ideas more efficiently and coherently.

And a native speaker will quickly realize that you are a learner of English as a foreign language when you have a grammatical error such as "I meet her yesterday". It is a common mistake but it is necessary to own good English grammar. It is crucial to be good at grammar because it also shows respect for the culture. Grammar gives insights into the meaning and contents of the words. Understanding and responding will be appropriately and fluently. Especially, when using English for academic purposes, grammar is extremely important and indispensable. (Thornbury, 1999; 213) states two main types of CLT; the first one is the shallow-end approach and the second one is the deep-

end approach. Although the deep-end approach also has strong influences, the paper does not mention too much about "the deep-end approach" as it is not useful and unnecessary. The study only considers more about the "shallow-end approach". (Thornbury, 1999;18) refers to the shallow-end approach to Communicative Language Teaching is based on the thought that to make the learners use language in a communicative situation, it is necessary first to learn the grammatical rules and then apply them in that communicative situation.

In the shallow-end approach, CLT deals with grammar. Firstly, it will include the grammatical structures using in communication; Secondly, it considered about functional grammar. (Halliday, 1985; 5) demonstrates that grammar is the study of linguistic forms or wordings realizing functions or meanings; both wordings and functions are studied by the grammar. English Grammar is considered as a vital means towards communication. It is taught widely in shallow-end syllabuses to acquire using English grammar communication.

As it is known that learners presented grammatical rules only learn by heart presentation-practice-production cycle) but rather, the teachers provide them with examples. From which the learners will have to infer the rules by themselves and have more creative ways to make the dialogues when using the language. Students will have more opportunities to practice using the language as well as to see the relevance outside the classroom. It stimulates critical thinking for the students in different conversations.

Educational Implications

The implications of the study include the critical look at the roles of English Grammar in CLT in the EFL/ESL context. Firstly, the research mentions activities. It should have combined useful forms and practical activities, incorporating communicative activities, authentic materials, personalized contexts, and diversified activities. When teaching grammar, teachers should organize some activities which must be combined between the content of grammar and entertainment activities. It should be ensured that the activity can bring much success to the grammar lesson.

The students feel relax and unpressured. Sometimes it should have more activities from the students and they can incorporate with their teacher or self-organized by themselves under teachers' instruction. Their study will much be better and flexible. They can enjoy working with the tasks as well as with teachers and friends. Learners can do individually; work in pairs or groups to exchange ideas. Also, interpersonal exchanges are good ways to unlock new things. Besides, role-playing which is related to actual life also should be organized for students and students can pretend to be someone in different situations. It helps to keep remembering the words and sentences longer.

Secondly, it discusses teacher roles. Teachers have important roles in the classroom. Teachers should have good methods to bring learners to real-world situations. Moreover, the teachers' roles are the instructor, sampler, and assessor by giving feedback, giving correction, and extending matters. The most important matter is the teachers' instruction. If teachers have clear instruction it will help learners follow the correct steps. (Richards & Rodgers, 2001;167) explain that "a language teacher is no longer viewed as the authority of the knowledge, but as a facilitator, participant, and group manager who could create a productive learning environment for the learners".

Besides, teaching should be flexible and practical. The teacher should show how to plan a communicative grammar lesson, how to arrange the steps in teaching. Teachers should prepare CLT activities, plan lessons, and create a CLT environment to develop the communicative competence of the students. The form and content must be suitable, meaningful, and related to the student's life. Teachers should know how to balance, how to combine their teaching approach to get effective results. Also, it is important to provide real contexts, recall it over and over (practice makes perfect) and the teacher should give students the chance to make mistakes and self-correct their own mistakes. The teachers give the final corrections, feedbacks, and directions. To provide a better opportunity to enhance learners' communicative competence, teachers should make real communication focus on language learning.

Teachers should provide learners opportunities to develop both accuracy and fluency in a CLT environment or teachers should link different skills such as speaking, reading, writing, and listening to train learners' abilities such as discussion, communication games, and information exchanges about the students themselves or role-play following the suitability of the target grammatical points. Teachers should give feedbacks and some necessary explanations. After the presentation, teachers will create controlled practice tasks that are based on the principles.

(Harmer, 1991; 122) points out some communicative activities about discussions, communication games and information exchanges among students, or role-play by the suitability of the target grammatical points. (Platt and Platt, 1992; 179) state that communicative language teaching is defined as an approach to foreign or second language teaching which aims to develop communicative competence. Furthermore, grammar lesson teaching should be authentic and easy to conduct. It can be used very often in daily life. Thirdly, it is about the learner roles. They should show cooperation, interaction, give feedback, and comments. If students want to improve communication with grammar, students should own a solid foundation in the form, meaning, and use of grammatical structures. They can understand better and use skilfully their target language.

Learners should own basic grammar at least and they need to accumulate necessary grammar knowledge in communication. They should be self-conscious about their studies. Moreover, studying materials are also very important. The materials should be updated regularly, edited, revised, and reformed suitably with the present's requirement. There are many documents about communicative activities, authentic materials, and personalized contexts. Indeed, course books are also developed on the traditional method of language teaching. (May, 1998; 716) states that with learner-oriented classrooms, opportunities to develop a wide repository of activities, multiple roles of the teachers, and the use of authentic materials. It is essential to update new programs for teaching and studying. Besides, the school administration should improve the traditional method of teaching, schooling syllabus, and materials. There should be supports in teaching and diversified activities. Administrators may support teachers about device aids as well as different resources of CLT. It should have some supported things from machines, sounding, display devices, facilitation, Administrators should encourage teachers to design or re-design curriculum in developing students' communicative competence in daily activities. To sum up, the combination of activities, teachers, learners, and materials are very necessary for teaching and learning English grammar communicatively. It needs to be upgraded and consolidated each time. It must be satisfactory and meet the needs of learners and society. Otherwise teaching grammar must bring benefits to learners.

Conclusion

The study contains three main points of discussing grammar teaching including principles and goals of grammar teaching, the positions and roles of grammar in communicative language teaching (CLT) in the EFL/ESL context, and some educational implications on how to teach Grammar communicatively in the EFL/ESL context. Teaching English grammar communicatively plays a vital role in teaching and learning a language. Especially, without grammar knowledge, the understandable sentences cannot be comprehended.

It has no meaning and sense. The conversation may be good at content but it can be bad at grammar so it also causes confusion to listeners and they cannot get the full meaning. Because people need to understand what others speak out then they can give exact responses. When teaching grammar, the teachers not only give the students the means to express themselves but also fulfil their expectations of what learning a foreign language involves. In conclusion, grammar teaching plays an indispensable role in learning EFL/ESL. Grammar should be taught in learning English communication. The Grammar Translation Method is concerned with accuracy and fluency while the Communicative Approach emphasizes fluency.

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